

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Thiosemicarbazones and Hydrazones Derived from Indanone-1

VINAY S. MISRA ; RAJENDRA S. VARMA and (Miss) SHAKUNTALA AGARWAL

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow

Manuscript received 22 March 1975 accepted 29 May 1975.

A series of thiosemicarbazones and hydrazones has been synthesised by the condensation of indanone-1 with various arylthiosemicarbazides and carboxylic acid hydrazides. The compounds thus synthesised have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity.

THIOSEMICARBAZONES and hydrazones are biologically versatile compounds displaying antibacterial¹⁻⁶, antifungal⁷, anticancer^{8,9}, antiviral¹⁰⁻¹⁶ and MAO inhibitory properties¹⁷. *p*-acetamidobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone¹⁸ is a clinically effective drug against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Likewise isatin- β -thiosemicarbazone¹⁹ is a well known antiviral agent. N-Dialkylaminomethylisatin- β -thiosemicarbazones (e. g. I) synthesised by Varma and Nobles have shown pronounced antibacterial and antifungal activity²⁰.

Furthermore, nitrofurfurylidene isatin-3-hydrazones²¹ have also demonstrated antibacterial activity. Since the isatin (II) nucleus resembles indanone (III) nucleus it may be conceived that similar compounds obtained from indanone-1 would elicit similar biological response, because isosteric substances²² are known to possess similar activity. With this view in mind we have synthesised a series of thiosemicarbazones (IV) and hydrazones (V) derived from indanone-1.

Thiosemicarbazides²³ were obtained by successively treating amines with carbondisulfide/ammonia, sodium-chloroacetate and hydrazine hydrate. Hydrazides²⁴ were obtained by the hydrazinolysis of the methyl esters of the carboxylic acids. These were then condensed with III, which was prepared by the cyclisation of hydrocinnamic acid^{25,26}, to furnish IV and V.

TABLE—1

S. No.	R	M.P.°C	Molecular formula	N analyses %	
				Calcd	Found
<i>Indanone-1-thiosemicarbazones (IV)</i>					
1.	C ₆ H ₅	198	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	14.94	14.41
2.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	160	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	14.23	14.10
3.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	143	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	14.23	14.02
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	163	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	14.23	13.98
5.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	145	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	13.50	13.35
6.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	149	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	13.50	13.42
7.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	170	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	13.50	13.21
8.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	126	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	13.31	13.09
9.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	150	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	13.31	13.15
<i>Indanone-1-hydrazones (V)</i>					
10.	C ₆ H ₅	155	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	11.20	10.98
11.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OH	250d	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	10.52	10.16
12.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OH	265d	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	10.52	10.23
13.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OH	240d	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	10.52	10.41
14.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	181	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O	9.84	9.60
15.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	220d	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃	14.23	14.10
16.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	205	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃	14.23	14.05
17.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br	187	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O	8.51	8.18
18.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅	180	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	9.52	9.41

TABLE—2 ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF THIOSEMICARBAZONES (IV) AND HYDRAZONES (V)

Compound No.	Microbial spectrum			
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
1.	—	+	+	—
3.	—	+	—	—
5.	+	+	—	—
6.	+	+	—	—
7.	+	—	—	—
8.	—	+	+	—
9.	—	+	—	—
11.	—	+	—	—
12.	—	—	—	+
15.	—	—	—	+
16.	—	—	+	+
17.	—	—	—	+

+, inhibition. —, no inhibition

Biological data : The compounds listed in Table 1 were evaluated for their inhibitory effects against four organisms, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus megaterium* by agar diffusion technique²⁷. The agar medium was inoculated with a 24 hr old culture of the test organism. Filter paper discs (5 mm diameter) saturated with the solution of the test compound (10 mg/ml in ethanol or acetone) were placed on the agar plate after drying up the solvent. After an incubation period of 36 hr. the zones of inhibition around the discs were measured. The compounds showing antibacterial activity are reported in Table 2.

Experimental

Indanone-1 was prepared from hydrocinnamic acid^{25,26}.

Arylthiosemicarbazides were synthesised according to procedures reported in the literature²⁸.

Benzoic acid hydrazides were obtained from corresponding methyl esters and hydrazine hydrate²⁴.

Indanone-1-thiosemicarbazones (IV) : (Table 1) To a boiling solution of indanone-1 (0.01 mole) in 25 ml of ethanol, an appropriate arylthiosemicarbazide (0.01 mole) was added in one lot. The resulting reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 1 hr. The contents of the flask were then cooled and the solid product which separated out was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Indanone-1-hydrazones (V) : (Table 1). Indanone-1 (0.01 mole), a suitable hydrazide (0.01 mole) and 20 ml of ethanol were taken in a 100 ml. flask. The contents of the flask were refluxed for 1 hr on a steam bath. The solid mass thus obtained was recrystallised from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. Nitya Nand, Director C.D.R.I. and Dr. S. A. Imam, Scientist C, C.D.R.I. for microanalysis and bioassay respectively. They are also indebted to the Head of the department of chemistry, Lucknow University for providing the necessary facilities. One of us (S. A.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance.

References

1. G. DOMAGK, *Naturwiss*, 1946, 33, 315.
2. R. BEHNISCH, F. MIETZSCH and H. SCHMIDT, *Angew. Chem.*, 1948, 60, 113.
3. N. P. BUU-HOI, M. WELSCH, G. DECHAMPS, H. L. BIHAN, F. BINON and N. D. XUONG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 121.
4. R. S. VARMA, K. C. GUPTA, AMARNATH and V. S. MISRA, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1964, 4, 63.
5. W. L. NOBLES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 6675.
6. H. C. CALDWELL and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Ed.*, 1956, 45, 729.
7. D. M. WILES, B. A. GINGRAS and T. SUPRUNCHUK, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 1735.
8. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, JR., *Cancer Res.*, 1966, 26, 1638.
9. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, JR., *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, 9, 585.
10. P. W. SADLER, D. G. O' SULLIVAN and D. J. BAUER, *Antibiot. Chemothep.*, 1963, 2, 403.
11. D. BUTTIMORE, D. H. JONES, R. SLACK and K. R. H. WOOLDRIDGE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2032.
12. R. SLACK, K. R. H. WOOLDRIDGE, J. A. MCFADZEAN and S. SQUIRES, *Nature*, 1964, 204, 587.
13. R. L. THOMPSON, S. A. MINTON, J. A. OFFICER and G. H. HITCHINGS, *J. Immunol.*, 1953, 70, 229.
14. E. CAMPAIGNE, R. L. THOMPSON and J. E. VAN WERTH, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1959, 1, 577.
15. D. J. BAUER and P. W. SADLER, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1960, 15, 101.
16. D. HAMRE, J. BERNSTEIN and R. DONOVICK, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1950, 73, 275.
17. J. P. DARWIN, A. SHORE and B. B. BRODIE, *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, 80, 643.
18. G. DOMAGK, SCHWEIZ, *Z. Path. Bakt.*, 1949, 12, 575.
19. H. E. WHIPPLE, *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1965, 130, 71.
20. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, (in press).
21. A. C. PADHYA, H. J. MEHTA, V. S. DIGHE and S. SOMAS-EKHARA, *Science and Culture*, 1973, 39, 55.
22. A. BURGER, "Medicinal Chemistry", 2nd Ed. Interscience Publishers, Inc. New York, 1960, p. 72.
23. V. S. MISRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 553.
24. V. S. MISRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 763.
25. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longman Group Ltd., London, 1971, p. 474.
26. W. F. HICKINBOTTOM, "Reaction of Organic Compounds", Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1957, p. 89.
27. R. S. VARMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1973, 13, 43.